

COMPUTER MODELING OF THE PROCESSES OF INTERACTION OF METAL ATOMS WITH THE FULLERENE C₆₀ MOLECULE

¹Umirzakov Baltokhodja, ²Jabborov Khayitmurod, ³Yadgarov Ishmumin

¹Professor, Tashkent State Technical University named after I.A.Karimov

²Doctoral student, Tashkent State Technical University named after I.A.Karimov

³Professor, Institute of Ion-plasma and laser technologies of Uzbekistan Academy of Sciences

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15429685>

Abstract. *In this work, the M@C₆₀ complexes were studied, the highest interaction energy value was calculated for the Ni@C₆₀ complex, which shows the corresponding thermodynamic stability of this complex. The highest E_{int} value of the Ni@C₆₀ complex was determined to correlate very well with the shortest bond length, the M–C bond. The E_{int} values in the range from -3.59 to -8.54 eV were calculated for all the considered complexes, which additionally confirms the stability of the developed complexes.*

Keywords: *Fullerene, metal, carbon, single-atom catalyst, potential, molecule, bond, complex.*

Аннотация. *В данной работе изучены комплексы M@C₆₀, наибольшее значение энергии взаимодействия вычислено для комплекса Ni@C₆₀, что показывает соответствующую термодинамическую стабильность этого комплекса. Определены наибольшее значение E_{int} комплекса Ni@C₆₀ очень хорошо коррелирует с наименьшей длиной связи, связи M–C. Значения E_{int} в диапазоне от -3,59 до -8,54 эВ рассчитаны для всех рассмотренных комплексов, что дополнительно подтверждает стабильность разработанных комплексов.*

Ключевые слова: *Фуллерен, металл, углерод, одноатомный катализатор, потенциал, молекула, связь, комплекс.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu ishda M@C₆₀ komplekslari o'rganildi va ushbu kompleksning tegishli termodinamik barqarorligini ko'rsatadigan Ni@C₆₀ kompleksi uchun o'zaro ta'sir energiyasining eng yuqori qiymati hisoblab chiqildi. Ni@C₆₀ kompleksining eng yuqori E_{int} qiymati eng qisqa bog'lanish uzunligi M–C bilan juda yaxshi bog'liq. Ko'rib chiqilgan barcha komplekslar uchun -3.59 dan -8,54 eV gacha bo'lgan E_{int} qiymatlari hisoblab chiqilgan, bu esa ishlab chiqilgan komplekslarning barqarorligini yanada tasdiqlaydi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Fulleren, metal, uglerod, bir-atomli katalizator, potensial, molekula, bog'lanish, kompleks.*

Introduction. Carbon is an important element known for many years and exists in various forms such as diamond, graphite, conducting and semiconducting nanotubes and fullerenes. In the recent past, closed-cage fullerenes have attracted researchers due to their unique structures and properties. The fullerene molecule has a regular truncated icosahedron structure. It has 60 carbon atoms arranged at the vertices of a truncated icosahedron. The icosahedron structure has 90 equal-length edges, 60 identical vertices, 20 hexagonal faces and 12 pentagonal faces, forming a closed cage [1]. Due to the large size of the fullerene molecule compared to the doping alkali metal atoms or ions, the internal cavity in the C₆₀ molecule can accommodate numerous guest species [2]. Fullerenes have attracted considerable attention due to their interesting properties and potential

applications in various fields including materials science, chemistry, and medicine. Fullerenes, new allotropes of carbon, have attracted scientific attention since their discovery [3]. The empty space inside the fullerene cage is a good place to accommodate a wide range of atoms and small molecules [4]. Endofullerenes have been synthesized and studied by several experimental and theoretical methods [5,6,7].

Catalysts are currently considered as the basis of various commercial energy conversion procedures and industrial processes [8,9]. Transition metal (TM) catalysts are in great demand due to their low cost and excellent catalytic activity. Carbon materials are poised to become exceptional supports for (Single-atom catalysts) SACs due to their unique physical and chemical characteristics combined with their cost-effectiveness. In particular, fullerenes (C₆₀) are considered as excellent electron receptors and transporters [10]. Moreover, the spherical shape of C₆₀ provides a large surface area for catalytic activity, and its carbon framework can act as a substrate to support individual metal atoms. Therefore, we also investigated C₆₀ as a support material for single-atom catalysts (SACs). The aim of this work was to computer simulate the dynamics of metal atoms Ni (nickel), Ti (titanium), and Fe (iron) and fullerenes. In this study, we constructed several models by incorporating individual transition metal (TM) atoms with fullerene (M@C₆₀). Then, the bond length, adsorption energy/interaction energy were calculated.

Methods and materials. The simulations were performed using the Large-scale Atomic/Molecular Massively Parallel Simulator (LAMMPS) package [11]. The simulation configurations were visualized using the Jmol software [12]. The potential of the carbon-metal (Me) system can be defined as the sum of three potential energies of interactions carbon-carbon, carbon-Me and Me-Me, respectively:

$$U_{total} = U_{C-C} + U_{Me+Me} + U_{C-Me}. \quad (1)$$

The first part is intended to describe the interaction within the plane of the C₆₀ fullerene. For the C-C interaction, known potentials can be used, for example, the adapted empirical potential of intermolecular interaction AIREBO [13]. It is well tested and actively used to study carbon structures [14]. The potential consists of three parts:

$$E = \frac{1}{2} \sum_i \sum_{j \neq i} E_{ij}^{REBO} + E_{ij}^{LJ} + \sum_{k \neq i, j} \sum_{l \neq i, j, k} E_{kijl}^{TORSION}, \quad (2)$$

Where E_{ij}^{REBO} - is the energy of covalent interaction, E_{ij}^{LJ} - is the Van der Waals energy, $E_{kijl}^{TORSION}$ - is the energy of plane rotation.

We calculated the interaction energies (E_{int}) of the developed M@C₆₀ complexes using the following equation:

$$\Delta E_{int} = E_{M@C60} - (E_{C60} + E_M) \quad (3)$$

Here, $E_{M@C60}$ refers to the energy of the complex, while E_{C60} and E_M — are the energies of the isolated C₆₀ nanocage and the transition metal atom with the most stable spin state, respectively.

Results and discussion. The developed M@C₆₀ complexes were optimized to their most stable geometry before adsorption using the LAMMPS package and the adapted empirical intermolecular interaction potential AIREBO. The C₆₀ fullerene molecule has two bond lengths. The 6:6 ring bonds (between two hexagons) can be considered as “double bonds”, they are shorter (1.401 Å) than the 6:5 bonds (1.458 Å, between a hexagon and a pentagon). The weighted average bond length is 1.44 Å. The calculated geometry of the C₆₀ fullerene, both from the top and from the side, is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Top view (a) and side view (b) of the optimized structure of fullerene C_{60} with a C–C bond length of 1.45 Å (b6,5 bond), calculated using the LAMMPS package.

Moreover, the first-row transition metal atoms are exohedrally doped on the C_{60} nanocage at different doping sites, i.e., at the apex of the pentagons and at the b6,5 interface. In all the considered $M@C_{60}$ complexes, the most stable complex is observed at the b6,5 interface.

The optimized ground state geometries along with the C–M (carbon-metal) bond lengths of the developed complexes are shown in Figure 2 and their corresponding interaction energies are listed in Table 1. It is obvious from Figure 2 that the interaction bond distances between the carbon atom of C_{60} fullerene and the transition metal are observed in the range of 1.91 to 2.10 Å, which mainly shows chemisorption. The shortest interaction distance is calculated for the $Ni@C_{60}$ complex (1.91 Å) for each Ni–C bond, followed by the $Fe@C_{60}$ complex (2.08 Å). In the case of the $Ni@C_{60}$ complex, the smallest bond value is also justified by the highest interaction energy (ΔE_{int}) value of –8.54 eV, while the largest interaction distance value of 2.10 Å is calculated for the $Ti@C_{60}$ complex for each Ti–C bond among all the developed complexes.

Table 1.

Interaction energies of a transition metal atom (M) with a C_{60} nanocage (ΔE_{int})

Complexes $M@C_{60}$	ΔE_{int} , eV
$Ni@C_{60}$	8.54
$Fe@C_{60}$	3.59
$Ti@C_{60}$	3.94

Figure 2. Optimized structures of stable $M@C_{60}$ ($M=Ni-Ti-Fe$) complexes with M–C bond distances calculated using the Airebo, Morse, Tersoff potential.

Besides the interaction distance, another important parameter for stability assessment is the interaction energy. The interaction energy of $M@C_{60}$ complexes is calculated using formula 5, and the interaction energy values in different spin states are related to their unpaired electrons (see Table 1). The negative sign of the interaction energy values indicates that doping of C_{60} nanocage with transition metal atoms is a simple process for all metal atoms (Ni–Ti–Fe). Among all the studied $M@C_{60}$ complexes, the highest interaction energy value is calculated for the $Ni@C_{60}$ complex, which shows the corresponding thermodynamic stability of this complex. The highest E_{int} value of the $Ni@C_{60}$ complex correlates very well with the shortest bond length, the M–C bond. The E_{int} values in the range from -3.59 to -8.54 eV are calculated for all the considered complexes, which further confirms the stability of the developed complexes. In general, no structural deformation is observed in any complex after optimization (see Figure 2). The results of the interaction energy analysis are also confirmed by the interaction distances of the M–C bond of the $M@C_{60}$ complexes.

Conclusion. A model experiment of the interaction of metal atoms (Ni, Ti, Fe) with the surface of the C_{60} fullerene molecule was conducted. It was found that the adsorption of the transition metal on the C_{60} fullerene is exothermic for all the metals under consideration, and the highest interaction energy was calculated for the $Ni@C_{60}$ complex. The highest value of E_{int} for the $Ni@C_{60}$ complex was determined to correlate very well with the shortest bond length, the M–C bond.

Acknowledgments. The work was supported by the project FL-8323102108 "Synthesis and modification of functional carbon-based nanomaterials, study of the processes of their interaction with atomic particles" of the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

REFERENCES

1. Dresselhaus, M. S., Dresselhaus, G., & Eklund, P. C. (1996). Carbon Materials. Science of Fullerenes and Carbon Nanotubes, 15–59. [doi:10.1016/b978-012221820-0/50002-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-012221820-0/50002-2)
2. Shobhna Dhiman, Ranjan Kumar & Keya Dharamvir. Optimized interaction parameters for metal-doped endohedral fullerene. Appl Nanosci (2017) 7:137–143. [DOI 10.1007/s13204-017-0556-0](https://doi.org/10.1007/s13204-017-0556-0)
3. Kroto H W, Heath J R, O'Brien S C, Curl R F and Smalley R E. C_{60} : Buckminsterfullerene. Nature volume 318, pages 162–163 (1985) [doi:10.1038/318162a0](https://doi.org/10.1038/318162a0)
4. Akasaka T and Nagase S 2002 Endofullerenes: A New Family of Carbon Clusters, Kluwer, Dordrecht
5. Shinohara, H (2000) Endohedral metallofullerenes. Reports on Progress in Physics, 63 (6). 843-892 [doi:10.1088/0034-4885/63/6/201](https://doi.org/10.1088/0034-4885/63/6/201)
6. Wang C R, Kai T, Tomiyama T, Yoshida T, Kobayashi Y, Nishibori E, Takata M, Sakata M and Shinohara H. C_{66} fullerene encaging a scandium dimer. Nature 2000 Nov 23; 408(6811):426-7. [doi: 10.1038/35044195](https://doi.org/10.1038/35044195)
7. A. Dawid and K. Górný. Dynamics of endohedral fullerene $K^+@C_{60}$ inside single walled carbon nanotube: MD simulation TASK Quarterly: scientific bulletin of Academic Computer Center in Gdansk. Vol. 13, No. 1-2. pp.83-91. 2009.
8. S. Sarfaraz, M. Yar, Nadeem S. Sheikh, I. Bayach and Kh. Ayub. Transition Metal-Doped C_{20} Fullerene-Based Single-Atom Catalysts with High Catalytic Activity for Hydrogen

- Dissociation Reaction. ACS Omega 2023, 8, 15, 14077-14088. [DOI: 10.1021/acsomega.3c00721](https://doi.org/10.1021/acsomega.3c00721)
9. Yang, X.-F.; Wang, A.; Qiao, B.; Li, J.; Liu, J.; Zhang, T. Single atom catalysts: a new frontier in heterogeneous catalysis. Acc. Chem. Res. 2013, 46, pp. 1740–1748. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ar300361m>
 10. Xiaoqing Liu, Rui Chen, Wei Peng, Lichang Yin, De'an Yang. Multiatom activation of single-atom electrocatalysts via remote coordination for ultrahigh-rate two-electron oxygen reduction J. Energy Chem. Volume 76, pp. 622-630 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jechem.2022.10.015>
 11. Andrea A., Eve le Guillou, Antoine Danzé, Irene Moulitsas, Iwan H. Sahputra, Amin Rahmat, Xiaocheng Shang. // How to Modify LAMMPS: From the Prospective of a Particle Method Researcher. ChemEngineering 2021, 5(2), 30; <https://doi.org/10.3390/chemengineering5020030>
 12. Robert Hanson. Jmol—A paradigm shift in crystallographic visualization // September 2010. Journal of Applied Crystallography 43(5). [DOI:10.1107/S0021889810030256](https://doi.org/10.1107/S0021889810030256)
 13. Xueming Yang, Sihan Wu, Jiangxin Xu, Bingyang Cao, Albert C. To // Spurious heat conduction behavior of finite-size graphene nanoribbon under extreme uniaxial strain caused by the AIREBO potential. Physica E: Low-dimensional Systems and Nanostructures. Volume 96, February 2018, Pages 46-53. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.physe.2017.10.006>
 14. Rysaeva, L. K., Baimova, J. A., Lisovenko, D. S., Gorodtsov, V. A., & Dmitriev, S. V. (2018). Elastic Properties of Fullerites and Diamond-Like Phases. Physica Status Solidi (b), 1800049. [doi:10.1002/pssb.201800049](https://doi.org/10.1002/pssb.201800049)